

GENDER AS A FACTOR IN AN EFFECTIVE SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION OF IN PRE-PUBESCENT PERIOD

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809546>

Nematova Nilufar

Uzswlu Master's Degree department

"English Linguistics and literature"

Group: 5

Abstrakt.

Ikkinchi tilni muvaffaqiyatli o'rganish o'ziga xos murakkab jarayon bo'lib ancha yillardan beri qizg'in o'rganilib kelinmoqda. Zero, bu masala har doim olimlar diqqat e'tiborida bo'lgan va bunga ta'sir etuvchi turli omillar, xususan, jinsning ahamiyati borasida ham bir necha izlanishlar amalga oshirilgan. Ushbu maqolada jinsning uch xil doiradagi til o'rganishga bo'lgan ta'siri yoritib beriladi. Ular: amaliy va no amaliy mashg'ulotlarni bajarish, miyaning ikkinchi til o'rganishdagi faoliyati hamda o'qituvchilarning ikki jins vakillariga dars jarayonidagi munosabatidan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar.

Ikkinchi tilni o'rganish, Jins, ayol va erkak nutqi, ritorik gaplar

Абстракт.

Эффективное овладение вторым языком – это уникальный процесс, который изучался с разных точек зрения в течение последних десятилетий. Тем не менее, поиск точных решений для улучшения качества преподавания иностранного языка никогда не переставал быть сложной задачей за счет повышения осведомленности о различных факторах, влияющих на эффективное изучение иностранного языка, таких как пол. В этой статье в основном делается попытка изучить роль пола с трех точек зрения, которые исследуют способности обоих полов выполнять задачи, связанные с производительностью и не связанные с производительностью, их функцию мозга в SLA и, наконец, обучение учителей иностранного языка в классе.

Ключевые слова.

SLA, пол, когнитивные способности, мужской язык, женский язык, вопросительные предложения.

Abstract.

Effective second language acquisition is a unique process that has been studied from different perspectives over the past decades. However, it has never stopped being a challenge to find out accurate solutions to improve the quality of teaching foreign language excellently

through raised awareness on various factors affecting to learn foreign language effectively such as gender. This paper mainly tries to study the role of gender from three perspectives which are investigating both genders' abilities in performance and non-performance related tasks, their brain function in SLA and finally, instructional delivery of foreign language teachers in classroom.

Key words.

SLA, gender, cognitive ability, male language, female language, interrogative sentences

SLA, Gender and Language Classes

It is worth mentioning one fact that in the past the issue of gender in second language acquisition was mainly neglected which was able to gain full attention to be studied as a factor in the late 1970s. As a result, over the last period there have appeared new interesting findings proven by real experiments conducted within a various range of age groups. Obviously, this marked a very important milestone in understanding better both men and women's cognitive abilities in acquiring foreign language. Furthermore, it facilitated the chance to apply more effective approaches, methods and strategies in teaching both genders. Aslan (2009) showed clearly in his study that both males and females tend to exploit various preferred learning strategies. This can be further supported in Gascoigne's study (2002), "males often apply interruptions, directives and sentence-first conjunctions. Females, on the contrary, often use interrogative sentences, justifiers, strong adverbs, personal pronouns and word-first adverbs." This mirrored vivid image of sociolinguistic issues present in language usage of either gender resulting in a massive upheaval regarding the dominance of either male or female in second language acquisition which was found to be more in favour of women's advantage in it as they are prone to apply new structures and to erase incorrect forms in interlanguage willingly (Ellis, 2012). This was further advocated by Bursell (1975), who conducted an empirical study amidst 6,000 British students of French aged 8. In the study, it was found that girls excelled extremely well in foreign language in contrast with the opposite sex members. Despite being one of the primitive researches in support of gender factor in second language acquisition, it paved the way for fundamental future investigations in detecting more accurate justifications to evaluate truly women's outperformance in acquiring foreign language.

Added to aforementioned points, it is essential to note that not only boys and girls apply different language forms in their speech but also it is scientifically

proven that their brain response to learning languages varies between each other. In 2008, a team of researchers at Northwestern university identified that in English language classes girls' brain worked more intensively than the boys' (Burman, Bitan and Booth, 2008). Boys and girls aged between 9 and 15 with equal number of 31 respectively were chosen by researchers to carry out the investigation in which functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) was applied while their completing several spelling and writing exercises. The subjects were required to read the word and identify its meaning with no exposure to hearing or seeing them. It was found that girls' brain demonstrated higher activation in the areas connected with critical thinking and speech producing while boys' brain lagged behind in auditory and visual performance. The study draws the conclusion that males rely heavily upon their senses, in contrast, females use more structural approach in language learning (Burman, Bitan, & Booth, 2008). Furthermore, researchers Arabski and Wojtaszek (2011) claimed that in general, males often dominate in the fields that apply senses such as reading and writing exercises and videos. They show better performance in oral exams with more visual aids than females. By contrast, females' brain is geared for producing speech, doing grammar exercises involving more critical thinking skills such as gap filling or verb conjugations. Consequently, in an exam with speaking part girls outperform boys. Also, it is well-known fact that language exams are designed to check grammar, writing and speaking competence of learners which explains why females are in favour of further career pursuit in language domain area as they have high potential to perform excellently in language examinations than men often do. Similarly, relevant research conducted by van der Silk, van Hout, and Schepens (2015, as cited in Wightman, 2020) revealed very important information in justifying female's dominance. In that study, adults from 88 countries learning Dutch as a foreign language with different 49 language backgrounds were selected as subjects. Interestingly, this time, unlike to researchers at Northwestern University, there was no gap between males and females' performance in reading and listening tasks. They concluded that men often lose their advantage in those areas as they grow older. However, women are able to retain a lifelong capability to excel in writing and speaking components from their childhood.

The evaluation of gender issues from the perspective of performance-related areas has thoroughly been studied which raises another crucial concern of analysing both genders' capabilities in no performance related circumstances. Kettemann et al (1998) initiated this approach in a study conducted among both

primary and secondary school pupils across several countries of Europe which explored learner's assumptions on three following categories:

- popular subject among boys and girls
- strategies used by both of them
- their attitudes for learning a language

Even though there was no sufficient data to support the role of strategies applied by both genders for most of the researchers. Bacon and Finnemann (1992, as cited in Feery, 2008) were able to sift the information supporting the effect of strategies as well as stressing the fact that there is a staggering contrast between male and female's inspiration for learning a language. In addition, Kettemann (1998) pointed that with regards to motivation girls presented more optimistic view about foreign language acquisition compared to boys. In a study by Baumert (as cited in Feery, 2008), a similar conclusion was deduced with additional support which is that there is a greater level of ambition for language learning in unisex schools. According to Kettemann (1992), the reason why gender-related differences exists can be explained by three main categories: "biological stance, a cognitive-psychological approach and a socialisation theory-based approach." However, it is essential to note here that reaching to ultimate answer to above-mentioned theories is rather limited as it remains unclear which area was their main focus.

In contrast with previous studies, Alysson Jule (2004) attempted to investigate gender-related language learning issues from a perspective of instruction received in language classes. In particular, her experiment priorities were not to discuss gender specific characteristics rather it addressed the issues like identity construction, power relations, the role of the classroom and the sessions that occur within the classroom. Particularly, it analyses the role of gender involvement in classroom practices, or lack of it, especially, in language learning lessons. It mainly studies range of methods or approaches teachers opt for applying in the lesson in which primary aim is to check whether these methods affect in gendered behavior's, precisely, are they mostly girls-orientated or boys-orientated? Jule believes that by observing more closely a person can understand the relationship of gender to SLA process at ease. The point here is that teaching methods can have an impact upon the development of learners regarding their preference in learning foreign languages. She sheds light over the issue by referring to numerous researches which have concluded that both male and female teachers are often attentive to boys in the class ignoring girl's importance which results in either motivating or demotivation either of the sexes. In general, according to Jule (2004),

it was suggested that teachers should give preference on equality while selecting a method applicable in the classroom being aware of both genders' role in teaching. In other words, they should set the classroom procedures accordingly presenting opportunity for active involvement from both boys and girls. Her findings based upon her own experiment reveal another key factor which is that in addition to performance and no performance related issues there is a role of classroom management by teacher's side which might have an effect on creating the gap between males and females' SLA process.

As a final note, it can be said that current perspectives on the role of gender issues in SLA have altered totally different than the way it was before. However, it should be born in mind that these attempts are the only start-up projects for future new initiatives needing further investigations and authentic relevant experiments conducted on a massive scale. In general, this review of literature, on the account of gender as a factor in second language acquisition, has presented brief summary of what areas of gender issues have been studied so far. It primarily supports the notion that females are better in learning foreign language due to the factors mentioned earlier in this paper. According to it, women are both psychologically and mentally more prone to adapt easily to new structures, rules in second language which is believed to be the result of their openness to novel ideas. In addition to this, language learning environment can have a substantial influence which may result in either of the genders becoming dominant in SLA process, to be more precisely, not only women's brain functioning but also social factors happening in language classroom may lead them to outperform in language learning. Afterall, even though this paper has given an overall picture of gender importance in SLA it has not covered matters such as culture which is another essential factor prior to making final judgement on the dominance of either gender in second language acquisition. Thus, the role of cultural background in effective second language acquisition has been left intact which should be another crucial target in future investigations.

REFERENCES:

1. Aslan, O. (2009). *The role of gender and language learning strategies in learning English*. Unpublished Master's thesis

2. Arabski, P. J., & Wojtaszek, A. (Eds.). (2011). *Individual learner differences in SLA*. Retrieved from <https://ebookcentral-proquest-com.proxy.lib.utk.edu>
3. Burman, D. D., Bitan, T., & Booth, J. R. (2008). Sex differences in neural processing of language among children. *Neuropsychologia*, 46(5), 1349-1362. doi:10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2007.12.021
4. Burstall, C. (1975). French in the primary school: The British experiment. *Canadian Modern Language Review*, 31, 388-402.
5. Ellis, R. (2012). *The study of second language acquisition* (2nd ed.). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
6. Feery, K. (2008) "Current Perspectives on the Role of Gender in Second Language Acquisition (SLA) Research," *The ITB Journal: Vol. 9: Iss. 1, Article 4*. doi:10.21427/D7DB3H
7. Gascoigne, C. (2002). The role of gender in L2 interaction: Socialization via L2 materials. *Encuentro Revista de Investigación e Innovación en la Clase de Idioma*, 13/14, 81-89
8. Julé, A. (2004). *Gender, Participation and Silence in the Language Classroom: Sh-Shushing the Girls*. New York.
9. Kettemann, B./Cossée, M./Kerschbaumer, M./Landsiedler, I. (1998), Fremdsprachen - Mädchensache? Geschlechtsspezifische Aspekte des Fremdsprachenerwerbs in der Schule. In: *Moderne Sprachen: Zeitschrift des Verbandes der Österreichischen Neuphilologen* 42: 11-25.
10. Wightman, M. (2020) "Gender Differences in Second Language Learning: Why They Exist and What We Can Do About It" Chancellor's Honors Program Projects